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A FREQUENCY-DOMAIN APPROACH FOR DAMAGE DETECTION IN WELDED STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

The goal of the present paper is to apply a multiaxial fatigue criterion, formulated in frequency-domain, to welded components. In particular, the proposed procedure requires: (i) to evaluate the stress field at the so-called hot-spot; (ii) to compute the fatigue damage. A case study, represented by fillet-welded tubular T-joints under random loading, is examined to assess the validity of the above procedure in estimating the crack nucleation position. Finally, the above theoretical results are also compared with those derived by means of a similar procedure, which has recently been proposed by some of the present authors, but formulated in time-domain.

KEYWORDS: fillet-welded joints; hot-spot approach; frequency-domain criterion; multiaxial random fatigue.

1. INTRODUCTION

In situations of practical interest, engineers engaged in manufacturing process design high-performance mechanical components by efficiently joining their various parts. The widely adopted joining technology is represented by welding, which also plays a primary role in repairs of structural components¹. However, as is well-known, the fatigue strength of a welded component in presence of multiaxial cyclic loading is significantly lower than that of a un-welded one (even if the components are made of the same material)². In particular, the factors causing the above strength reduction³⁻⁵ are: residual stresses⁶⁻⁹, thermal distortions¹⁰, defects caused by partial penetration¹¹, and material microstructural imperfections¹².

Moreover, complex time-variable load histories applied to welded components result in severe stress/strain gradients at the weld toes/roots leading to fatigue damage near such critical regions.

In presence of constant amplitude multiaxial cyclic loading, several fatigue criteria have been proposed for the fatigue assessment of welded components by taking full advantage of both well-established methodologies and experimental investigations¹³. In particular, such criteria usually implement three different approaches in order to compute the weld stress field¹⁴: the nominal stress approach, the structural hot-spot stress approach, and the effective notch stress approach. Among those available in the technical literature, the criteria proposed by Sonsino et al.¹⁵⁻¹⁹, Takahashi et al.^{20,21} and Berto et al.²²⁻²⁴ deserve to be mentioned.

On the contrary, only few attempts have been made so far to devise sound criteria capable of accurately estimating fatigue damage when welded mechanical assemblies are subjected to variable amplitude multiaxial cyclic loading²⁵⁻²⁹. In presence of such a loading, flexible structural components usually operate at or close to their natural frequencies with a consequent reduction in fatigue life. It is common to assume that the input random loading as well as the stress/strain response of the structural components are Gaussian and stationary. The validity of such an assumption is supported by the experimental evidence that several random loading following natural phenomena (such as sea waves, variable wind velocity, etc.) are Gaussian in character³⁰.

In such a context, some criteria have been formulated according to a frequency-domain approach³¹, where the damage estimation is directly obtained from the Power Spectral Density (PSD) function of local stress tensor components³²⁻⁴². Thanks to these features, the frequency-domain criteria minimize the analysis computational time with respect to the classical time-domain ones, especially in the case of long time loading histories⁴³.

According to the frequency-domain approach, the estimated damage is a function of the algorithm employed to count the loading cycles. Among the different procedures available in the literature, the Rain-Flow Counting (RFC) procedure, related to deterministic loading, is regarded to be the most accurate one⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶. However, the statistical distribution of the rain-flow is not known exactly and, consequently, the RFC damage is estimated only in an approximate way. The Readers

interested in the above approximated formulations can refer to Refs **[47-49]**.

In the last few years, a big effort has been made by some of the present authors to propose and systematically validate a random multiaxial fatigue criterion formulated in the frequency-domain⁵⁰⁻⁵². According to such a criterion, based on the well-known critical plane approach, the PSD function of an equivalent normal stress (evaluated on the critical plane) is adopted as the parameter to estimate the fatigue damage.

The present paper aims to extend the above Carpinteri et al. frequency-domain criterion⁵⁰⁻⁵² to practical situations involving welded components. Note that a similar strategy has recently been employed by some of the present authors using a time-domain fatigue criterion⁵³, obtaining satisfactory results in terms of fatigue damage prediction.

The novel procedure (reported in detail in **Section 2** and **Appendix A**) requires: (i) to evaluate the stress field at the verification point by means of the structural hot-spot stress approach; (ii) to compute the fatigue damage according to the Carpinteri et al. frequency-domain criterion.

The validation of such a procedure is reported in **Section 3** by analysing a case study (i.e. fillet-welded tubular T-joints of the H component of an agriculture sprayer), previously examined from both an experimental and a numerical point of view⁵⁴⁻⁵⁸.

The results obtained are discussed in **Section 4** by comparing the above theoretical results with those reported in Ref. [53]. Finally, some conclusions are drawn in **Section 5**.

2. FREQUENCY-DOMAIN CRITERION FORMULATION FOR WELDED COMPONENTS

In order to extend the frequency-domain multiaxial fatigue criterion by Carpinteri et al.⁵⁰⁻⁵² to welded components, the stress tensor at the so-called hot-spot (i.e. the verification point) has to be determined. As a matter of fact, when there is a high stress gradient such as that characterising the welded components, the procedure to determine the stress tensor at the verification point is fundamental in order to avoid too conservative fatigue life estimations. Therefore, the following procedure is adopted.

As has been previously mentioned, the stress tensor components are computed by means of the extrapolation equations proposed by the structural hot-spot stress approach¹⁴. More precisely, the stress components at the hot-spot depend on stresses at two reference points, which are located along the so-called extrapolation path (perpendicular to the weld toe/root) at certain distances from the hot-spot. Readers may find more details about the above extrapolation equations in Refs [14,53] related to type "a" hot spot and coarse mesh.

Once the stress tensor at the hot-spot is obtained, fatigue damage of welded components is computed by means of the Carpinteri et al. frequency-domain fatigue criterion⁵⁰⁻⁵². Such a criterion, proposed

for High Cycle Fatigue (HCF) regime, mainly consists of the following steps:

(a) definition of the critical plane orientation, which is regarded to be dependent on the stress tensor PSD matrix;

(b) evaluation of an equivalent stress PSD function related to the critical plane;

(c) estimation of the fatigue damage by means of the equivalent PSD function.

The flowchart of this criterion is shown in **Figure 1**, whereas its analytical formulation is detailed in **Appendix A**⁵⁰⁻⁵².

Figure 1.

3. VALIDATION THROUGH A CASE STUDY: H COMPONENT OF AN ARM SPRAYER

In order to assess the reliability in estimating fatigue damage of the proposed procedure, a case study (available in the literature) related to an H component of an agriculture sprayer (named arm sprayer in the following) is hereafter examined⁵⁴⁻⁵⁸. In particular, such an arm sprayer, installed on a tractor to pulverise herbicides and fungicides, is made of a metal truss structure (named bar in the following) with spray nozzles. The movement of the bar is allowed by the so-called H component (made of C25E steel), consisting of fillet-welded tubular T-joints (with tubular component thickness equal to 4.75 mm, whereas the leg length of the fillet welding is equal to 5 mm). Note that each T-joint is composed of: a chord

(tubular element characterised by a rectangular cross-section) and a brace (tubular element characterised by a circular cross-section).

The welding is carried out using a metal inert gas process. The fatigue parameters (i.e. fatigue strength under fully reversed normal and shear stress, and inverse slope of the S-N curve under fully reversed normal stress) of the welding material are computed according to the procedure proposed by Hanel e Haibach⁵⁹, as is reported in Ref. [54].

Under the agricultural sprayer service condition, the H component and its welded T-joints experience a multiaxial random fatigue stress state, and severe stress concentration phenomena occur near the weld toe. Due to such phenomena, the fillet-welded tubular T-joints represent the weakest links of the H component and several cracks occur under the above in-service multiaxial fatigue loading.

3.1 Experimental campaign

An experimental campaign was carried out in order to determine the strain state in the H structural component during the pulverisation process of herbicides in a Brazilian crop⁵⁴. The arm sprayer service condition, examined during the experimental campaign, consisted of the maneuvers listed in **Table 1**, each maneuver being performed with either full tank (containing herbicides and fungicides) or empty tank. Duration and repetition number of the above maneuvers during the H component life are reported in such a Table. Usually, a severe crack pattern in the H component is experimentally observed after

2000h of sprayer operations (see **Figure 3**) and, therefore, such a time interval is assumed to be the H component life.

Table 1

The strain field in the H component was measured at the control points W1 (on the outer side of the chord), W2 (on the inner side of the chord), and W3 (on the brace), as is reported in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2

Figure 3 shows the complete-bridge Wheatstone circuits arranged on both chords and brace:

- (i) two tee-rosettes were placed on each chord at points W1 and W2 (**Figures 3a-3d**);
- (ii) two fish-bone strain gages were placed on the brace at point W3 (**Figures 3e-3f**).

Figure 3

For each maneuver analysed, the time-history of the maximum principal strain was determined in the control points by taking full advantage of the experimental signals coming from the above three circuits. Note that, due to the symmetry of the structural configuration being examined, an averaging operation was carried out on the time histories of the maximum principal strain time at points W1 and W2 (chord) in order to obtain only one time history, which is named $\epsilon_{1,c}^{exp(n)}$ in the following (being n the number of the maneuver

reported in **Table 1**). On the other hand, the time history of the maximum principal strain at the control point W3 (brace) is indicated with $\epsilon_{1,b}^{exp(n)}$.

As an example, **Figures 4(a)** and **5(a)** report the time histories of the maximum principal strain in the chord and in the brace, respectively, for the maneuver named "U - curves" (No. 4.2 in **Table 1**) with empty tank. During this maneuver, the tractor made a U-curve passing through the planting rows.

Moreover, for the same maneuver, the probability density function and the amplitude spectrum (determined by applying the RFC method) of the maximum principal strain are plotted in **Figures 4(b)-4(c)** for the chord and in **Figures 5(b)-5(c)** for the brace. In particular, from the probability density function graphs, it can be noticed that the input signals follow a Gaussian probability distribution. The values of skewness and kurtosis are also computed in order to examine the deviation from normal distribution.

Further, from the amplitude spectrum plots, it can be deduced the loading cycle number for which the amplitude of the maximum principal strain is greater than a given value.

Figure 4

Figure 5

3.2 Numerical model

The multiaxial random stress state in the H component was numerically determined by means of a linear elastic FE (Finite Element) analysis⁵⁴ carried out by using the commercial software Ansys 14.5, Workbench 15. In particular, the H component was modelled with solid finite elements (prismatic and tetrahedral), and each T-joint was meshed according to Ref. [14], with a welding leg equal to 5mm.

The discretization adopted for the above FE analysis is reported in **Figure 6**, where the finite element mesh is assessed through a convergence analysis, being the minimum finite element size equal to about 0.7 mm.

The material properties of C25E steel, implemented in the numerical model, are listed in **Table 2**.

Table 2.

The forces transferred by the arm sprayer to the H component were numerically schematised by means of F_b and F_c , shown in **Figure 6**.

Figure 6

The numerical model⁵⁴ proved that the strain state at the control point W1 (or W2) on the chord only depended on the force F_c , whereas the strain state at the control point W3 on the brace only depended on the forces F_b . Therefore, the multiaxial stress state for each maneuver was straightforwardly determined: in the chords by applying

only the force F_c , whereas in the braces by applying only the forces F_b . It can be pointed out that the time histories related to the above forces were applied to the FE model by ensuring that the numerical principal strain time histories at the control points were the same as those from the experimental campaign.

The contour plot of the maximum principal stress is reported in **Figure 7** when only the force $F_c = 1$ is applied to the FE model. On the other hand, by applying only four forces $F_b = 1$, the contour plot of the maximum principal stress obtained from the FE analysis is shown in **Figure 8**.

Figure 7

Figure 8

3.3 Fatigue damage evaluation

Once the multiaxial stress state of the H component is numerically determined, the fatigue damage at the hot-spot is computed by applying both the structural hot-spot stress approach and the Carpinteri et al. frequency-domain criterion. The fatigue parameters used in such a calculation refer to the welding material^{53,54}.

More precisely, by considering the chord of the H component and the polar frame $O\alpha$ shown in **Figure 9**:

- I. a generic extrapolation path, starting from the origin O with an orientation α , is defined according the structural hot-spot stress approach¹⁴;
- II. the hot-spot is located at the intersection between the above path and the weld toe, being the distance from the origin O equal to d ;
- III. for each maneuver (**Table 1**), the stress components at the above hot-spot are determined by means of the structural hot-spot stress approach equations;
- IV. the Carpinteri et al. criterion is applied at the hot-spot for each maneuver, and the sum of the damages computed for all maneuvers during the H component life provides the total damage;
- V. the stress tensor calculation and the total fatigue damage estimation are repeated by varying the extrapolation path orientation α from 0° to 360° .

Then, the same procedure is performed for the brace.

Figure 9

Note that the orientation α is made to vary only from 0° to 180° (with an increment of 15°) and not from 0° to 360° . The above α range reduction is justified by the fact that, as is reported in Ref. [53], the total fatigue damage is practically equal to zero for $\alpha > 180^\circ$.

4. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

In order to evaluate the total damage, Carpinteri and co-workers⁴³⁻⁴⁵ proposed to determine the PSD Function (PSDF) of an equivalent normal stress, S_{eq} , related to the critical plane (as is reported in **Appendix A**).

In **Figure 10**, the one-sided PSDF G_{eq} of the equivalent normal stress related the chord is plotted for the orientation which maximises the total damage (i.e. α equal to 120°) and for maneuvers No. 3.2 (**Figure 10(a)**) and No. 4.2 (**Figure 10(b)**). Note that, in correspondence with the above maneuvers, the damage value for $\alpha=120^\circ$ is the minimum and the maximum, respectively.

Figure 10

A similar plot is shown in **Figure 11** for the brace. The PSDF G_{eq} is plotted for the orientation which maximises the total damage (i.e. α equal to 105°), examining maneuvers No. 3.2 (**Figure 11(a)**) and No. 4.2 (**Figure 11(b)**). Note that, in correspondence with the above maneuvers, the damage value for $\alpha=105^\circ$ is the minimum and the maximum, respectively.

Figure 11

The total damage vs orientation α curve is reported in **Figure 12(a)** for the chord and in **Figure 12(b)** for the brace.

A critical damage equal to 0.5 has been taken into account, such a value being recommended in fatigue design of welded structures and components¹⁴. According to **Figure 12**, it can be pointed out that the total damage is greater than the critical value for $50^\circ \leq \alpha \leq 145^\circ$ in the chord, and for $98^\circ \leq \alpha \leq 130^\circ$ in the brace.

Figure 12

In order to compare the above theoretical results with the experimental ones, the experimentally observed hot-spot positions were identified by means of a digitalisation procedure, as is reported in detail in Ref. [53]. In particular, such experimental hot-spot positions were identified in correspondence to α equal to about 71° and 110° , both in the chord and in the brace. It can be remarked that such experimental values fall inside the theoretical α interval for the chord, whereas the lower bound of the theoretical α range in the brace (i.e. $\alpha=98^\circ$) is slightly greater than the experimental one ($\alpha=71^\circ$). Nevertheless, the present formulation of the Carpinteri et al. criterion for welded components seems to be capable of accurately estimating the fatigue crack position on the weld toe.

Now the above results in terms of fatigue damage are compared with those determined by applying the Carpinteri et al. time-domain fatigue criterion⁵³ (**Figure 12**).

Even if total damage against orientation curves obtained by means of the above criteria have a similar shape, such curves move downward as the frequency-domain criterion is considered (especially for

$30^\circ \leq \alpha \leq 150^\circ$). Consequently, a better accuracy is achieved by considering the frequency-domain criterion, being the theoretical α range closer to the experimental one in comparison to the α interval determined through the time-domain criterion. Further, the present frequency-domain criterion has been proved to be much more computationally efficient than the time-domain one.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The present paper has been dedicated to propose and validate a procedure for fatigue damage evaluation of welded T-joints subjected to random loading by means of a frequency-domain approach. In particular, this novel procedure requires: (i) to evaluate the stress field at the verification point by means of the structural hot-spot stress approach; (ii) to compute the fatigue damage according to the Carpinteri et al. frequency-domain criterion.

Then, a case study (i.e. fillet-welded tubular T-joints of an arm sprayer) has been employed to evaluate the accuracy of such a procedure to estimate the fatigue crack initiation positions. The comparison between theoretical and experimental results related to crack nucleation position has been quite satisfactory, confirming the validity of the proposed procedure for welded joints.

Finally, the capabilities of the present criterion have been highlighted by comparing the theoretical results with those deduced by means of the time-domain formulation by Carpinteri et al.⁵³.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization: I.I., R.I.R. and S.V.; Methodology: A.C., I.I. S.V.; Validation: R.I.R., C.R., D.S. and A.Z.; Formal analysis: I.I., C.R., D.S., S.V. and A.Z.; writing—original draft preparation, C.R. and S.V.; writing—review and editing, A.C., R.I.R., D.S. and A.Z.; Funding acquisition: A.C., I.I., R.I.R. and S.V.

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Data Availability Statement

Data available on request due to privacy/ethical restrictions The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy or ethical restrictions.

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NOMENCLATURE

C_σ	coefficient of the normal stress S-N curve
$E[D_{NB}]$	expected fatigue damage per unit time by employing the narrow-band approximation
F_b, F_c	forces applied to the H component in the FE model
m	slope of the normal stress S-N curve
n	maneuver number (Table 1)
Ora	polar frame
$p_a(s)$	marginal probability distribution of the amplitude (s) of the counted cycles of loading
PXYZ	fixed frame
$P\hat{1}\hat{2}\hat{3}$	reference system of the weighted mean principal stress axes
Puvw	reference system attached to the critical plane
$S_{eq}(\omega)$	equivalent PSD function
$\mathbf{s}_{xyz}(t)$	stress vector referred to the reference system PXYZ
$\mathbf{s}_{uvw}(t)$	stress vector referred to the reference system Puvw
$\mathbf{S}_{xyz}(\omega)$	PSD matrix of $\mathbf{s}_{xyz}(t)$
$S_{i,j}(\omega)$	coefficients of the $\mathbf{S}_{xyz}(\omega)$ matrix
$S_{3',3'}$	PSD function of the normal stress σ_z
$S_{6',6'}$	PSD function of the shear stress $\tau_{y'z'}$
$\mathbf{S}_{uvw}(\omega)$	PSD matrix of $\mathbf{s}_{uvw}(t)$
$S_{3'',3''}$	PSD function of the normal stress σ_w
$S_{6'',6''}$	PSD function of the shear stress τ_{vw}
t	time
T_0	observation time interval
w	normal to the critical plane
$W1, W2, W3$	control points

δ	angle between the averaged direction $\hat{\mathbf{i}}$ and the normal \mathbf{W} to the critical plane
$\varepsilon_{1,b}^{exp(n)}$	experimental maximum principal strain time-history at point W3
$\varepsilon_{1,c}^{exp(n)}$	experimental maximum principal strain time-history at point W1, or equivalently, at point W2
λ_n	n-th spectral moment, with n positive real number
V_a	expected rate of occurrence of loading cycles
V_p	expected rate of occurrence of peaks of loading cycles
$\sigma_{af,-1}$	normal stress fatigue limit for fully reversed normal stress (loading ratio $R=-1$)
$\tau_{af,-1}$	shear stress fatigue limit for fully reversed shear stress (loading ratio $R=-1$)
ϕ, θ, ψ	Euler angles
ω	pulsation

Appendix A - Frequency-domain criterion

The criterion by Carpinteri et al.⁴³⁻⁴⁵ is here summarised.

First of all, some material fatigue properties (the fully reversed normal, σ_{af-1} , and shear, τ_{af-1} , stress fatigue limits and the slope, m , of the normal stress S-N curve) have to be set.

Then, let us consider a point P in the structural component subjected to a general time-varying random stress state. With respect to the fixed frame **PXYZ**, the stress tensor at point P is described by: $\mathbf{s}_{xyz}(t) = \{s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4, s_5, s_6\}^T = \{\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z, \tau_{xy}, \tau_{xz}, \tau_{yz}\}^T$.

By assuming that the stress tensor can be represented by a six-dimensional ergodic stationary Gaussian stochastic process with zero mean values, the matrix of Power Spectral Density (PSD) function, $\mathbf{S}_{xyz}(\omega)$, is expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{S}_{xyz}(\omega) = \begin{bmatrix} S_{1,1} & S_{1,2} & S_{1,3} & S_{1,4} & S_{1,5} & S_{1,6} \\ S_{2,1} & S_{2,2} & S_{2,3} & S_{2,4} & S_{2,5} & S_{2,6} \\ S_{3,1} & S_{3,2} & S_{3,3} & S_{3,4} & S_{3,5} & S_{3,6} \\ S_{4,1} & S_{4,2} & S_{4,3} & S_{4,4} & S_{4,5} & S_{4,6} \\ S_{5,1} & S_{5,2} & S_{5,3} & S_{5,4} & S_{5,5} & S_{5,6} \\ S_{6,1} & S_{6,2} & S_{6,3} & S_{6,4} & S_{6,5} & S_{6,6} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where ω is the pulsation.

A rotated frame $\hat{1}\hat{2}\hat{3}$, connected with the averaged principal stress directions $\hat{1}, \hat{2}, \hat{3}$, is looked for according to the following procedure (**Figure A.1**).

Figure A.1

Firstly, the direction $\hat{\mathbf{i}}$ (defined by the two Euler angles $\hat{\phi}, \hat{\theta}$ in **Figure A.1a**) is firstly computed so that s'_3 experiences its maximum value in a statistical sense, that is:

$$E\left[\max_{0 \leq t \leq T_0} s'_3(t)\right] \cong \sqrt{\lambda_0} \sqrt{2 \ln(N_1)} + \frac{0.5772}{\sqrt{2 \ln(N_1)}} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where λ_0 is the spectral moment of order 0 of the PSD function $S_{3',3'}$,

$$\lambda_0 = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} S_{3',3'}(\omega) d\omega \quad (\text{A.3})$$

and N_1 is a function of both the expected rate of mean zero-upcrossings of s'_3 (ν_0^+) and the observation period T_0 :

$$N_1 = \nu_0^+ T_0 = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_2}{\lambda_0}} T_0 = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |\omega|^2 S_{3',3'}(\omega) d\omega}{\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} S_{3',3'}(\omega) d\omega}} T_0 \quad (\text{A.4})$$

being λ_2 the spectral moment of order 2 of the PSD function $S_{3',3'}$.

Then, the direction $\hat{\mathbf{j}}$ (defined by the Euler angle $\hat{\psi}$ in **Figure A.1b**) is determined so that the variance of s'_6 is maximised:

$$\max_{0 \leq \psi \leq 2\pi} [\text{Var } s'_6] = \left[\max_{0 \leq \psi \leq 2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} S_{6',6'}(\omega, \hat{\psi}) d\omega \right] \quad (\text{A.5})$$

If the rotated frame $\hat{\mathbf{P}}\hat{\mathbf{1}}\hat{\mathbf{2}}\hat{\mathbf{3}}$ in **Figure A.1** is taken into account, the stress tensor at point P can be described by: $\mathbf{s}_{\hat{\mathbf{1}}\hat{\mathbf{2}}\hat{\mathbf{3}}}(t) = \{s'_1, s'_2, s'_3, s'_4, s'_5, s'_6\}^T = \{\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \tau_{12}, \tau_{13}, \tau_{23}\}^T$. The PSD matrix with respect to such a frame can be computed by means of the rotation matrix $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{C}(\hat{\phi}, \hat{\theta}, \hat{\psi})$:

$$\mathbf{S}_{\hat{1}\hat{2}\hat{3}}(\omega) = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{S}_{xyz}(\omega)\mathbf{C}^T \quad (\mathbf{A.6})$$

Then, the normal \mathbf{W} to the critical plane is linked to the averaged principal direction \hat{i} through an off-angle δ defined as follows (\mathbf{W} belongs to the principal plane $\hat{1}\hat{3}$, and the rotation is performed from \hat{i} to \hat{j} , **Figure A.2**):

$$\delta = \frac{3}{2} \left[1 - \left(\tau_{af,-1} / \sigma_{af,-1} \right)^2 \right] 45^\circ \quad (\mathbf{A.7})$$

where δ is expressed in degrees, and $\tau_{af,-1}$ and $\sigma_{af,-1}$ are the fatigue strengths at the reference number N_0 of loading cycles for fully reversed shear and normal stress, respectively.

Now the critical plane Δ , passing through point P, and the attached orthogonal frame $Puvw$ are considered (**Figure A.2**), where the u -axis is determined as the intersection between Δ and the plane defined by \mathbf{W} and the Z -axis. The angle between the averaged principal direction \hat{i} and the u -axis is named γ .

Figure A.2

The stress tensor at point P related to the frame $Puvw$ (**Figure A.2**) is named $\mathbf{s}_{uvw}(t) = \{s_1'', s_2'', s_3'', s_4'', s_5'', s_6''\}^T = \{\sigma_u, \sigma_v, \sigma_w, \tau_{uv}, \tau_{uw}, \tau_{vw}\}^T$. The u -axis defines the direction that maximizes the variance of the ergodic stationary Gaussian stochastic process s_6'' :

$$\max_{0 \leq \gamma \leq 2\pi} [\text{Var } s_6''] = \left[\max_{0 \leq \gamma \leq 2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} S_{\delta'', \delta''}(\omega) d\omega \right] \quad (\mathbf{A.8})$$

The PSD matrix with respect to such a frame can be computed by means of the rotation matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{C}} = \tilde{\mathbf{C}}(\gamma, \delta)$:

$$\mathbf{S}_{uvw}(\omega) = \tilde{\mathbf{C}} \mathbf{S}_{\hat{1}\hat{2}\hat{3}}(\omega) \tilde{\mathbf{C}}^T \quad (\text{A.9})$$

In order to reduce the multiaxial stress state to an equivalent uniaxial one, an equivalent PSDF is proposed to be computed through the following linear combination:

$$S_{eq} = S_{3',3''} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{af,-1}}{\tau_{af,-1}} \right) S_{6'',6'''} \quad (\text{A.10})$$

The expected fatigue damage per unit time, $E[D]$, may be evaluated by employing a linear cumulative damage rule:

$$E[D] = \nu_a C_\sigma^{-1} \int_0^{+\infty} s^k p_a(s) ds \quad (\text{A.11})$$

where ν_a is the expected rate of occurrence of loading cycles, m and C_σ are the parameters of the normal stress S-N curve ($\sigma^m N = C_\sigma$), and $p_a(s)$ is the probability distribution of the amplitude (s) of the counted equivalent stress cycles. Note that damage estimation in Eq.(A.11) depends on the algorithm used to count the loading cycles, i.e. it is related to the method adopted to estimate $p_a(s)$.

For strictly narrow-band Gaussian process, a closed-form solution is available to estimate the expected fatigue damage per unit time:

$$E[D_{NB}] = \nu_p C_\sigma^{-1} (\sqrt{2\lambda_0})^m \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{m}{2}\right) \quad (\text{A.12})$$

where λ_0 is the zero-order spectral moment of S_{eq} , Γ is the gamma function, and ν_p (the expected rate of peaks) is given by:

$$v_p = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_4}{\lambda_2}} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |\omega|^4 S_{eq}(\omega) d\omega}{\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} |\omega|^2 S_{eq}(\omega) d\omega}} \quad (\mathbf{A.13})$$

λ_2 and λ_4 being the spectral moments of order 2 and 4 of the PSD function S_{eq} .

A FREQUENCY-DOMAIN APPROACH FOR DAMAGE DETECTION IN WELDED STRUCTURES

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FIGURES AND TABLES

Figure 1. Flowchart of the Carpinteri et al. criterion⁵⁰⁻⁵².

Table 1. Sprayer service condition: duration and number of repetitions of each maneuver during the life cycle (corresponding to 2000 h).

MANEUVERS	No.	TANK	DURATION [s]	TIMES
Application of the herbicide (cultivated area)	1.1	Full	180	9000
	1.2	Empty	140	11572
Application of the herbicide (perimeter)	2.1	Full	40	18000
	2.2	Empty	52	13847
Braking	3.1	Full	10	18293
	3.2	Empty	23	7827
U - curves	4.1	Full	150	2400
	4.2	Empty	39	9231
Travel on unpaved road	5.1	Full	115	3120
	5.2	Empty	46	7913
Perimeter curves	6.1	Full	19	18948
	6.2	Empty	37	9864

Figure 2. Control points of the H component, where the strain measurements were performed.

A picture of the arm sprayer (an agricultural machine used to pulverize herbicides and fungicides in order to preserve crops against harmful insects and herbs) is also shown.

Figure 3. Bridge Wheatstone circuits arranged:

(a), (c) on the chords (outer side - point W1 in Fig.2); (b), (d) on the chords (inner side - point W2 in Fig.2); and (e), (f) on the brace (point W3 in Fig.2).

Figure 4. Maneuver No. 4.2 registered in the chord (duration equal to 39 sec): (a) time history, (b) probability density function, and (c) amplitude spectrum (computed by applying the rainflow counting method) of $\varepsilon_{I,c}^{exp(4.2)}$.

Figure 5. Maneuver No. 4.2 registered in the brace (duration equal to 39 sec): (a) time history, (b) probability density function, and (c) amplitude spectrum (computed by applying the rainflow counting method) of $\varepsilon_{I,b}^{exp(4.2)}$.

Figure 6. Discretization of the H structural component examined.

Table 2. Mechanical properties for C25E steel.

MATERIAL	E [GPa]	ν [-]	σ_u [MPa]	f_y [MPa]
C25E	198.0	0.3	470.0	≥ 230.0

Figure 7. Contour plot of the maximum principal stress (in MPa):

$$F_c = 1.0 \quad \text{and} \quad F_b = 0.0.$$

Figure 8. Contour plot of the maximum principal stress (in MPa):
 $F_c = 0.0$ and $F_b = 1.0$.

Figure 9. Schematic illustration of the novel fatigue damage evaluation procedure for the chord. Geometrical sizes of the examined T-joint are also shown (sizes in mm).

Figure 10. One-sided PSD function G_{eq} in the chord, in correspondence to $\alpha=120^\circ$ and $r=d$, for maneuvers (a) No. 3.2 and (b) No. 4.2.

Figure 11. One-sided PSD function G_{eq} in the brace, in correspondence to $\alpha=105^\circ$ and $r=d$, for maneuvers (a) No. 4.2 and (b) No. 5.2.

Figure 12. Total damage vs orientation α , computed by using both the time and the frequency domain criterion: (a) chord; (b) brace.